

TEACHERS IN THE NEW NORMAL: EXPLORING TEACHING STRATEGIES IN PUBLIC HIGH SCHOOLS

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ABSTRACT

This phenomenological study examined the teaching strategies used by public high schools in the new normal. It explored teachers' experiences associated with their implementation using the Transcendental phenomenology approach of Edmund Husserl (1964). The findings revealed 3 emerging themes with sub-themes on each theme of the teachers' lived experiences; (1) teachers' commonly used teaching strategies such as (1.1) collaborative and interactive strategies and (1.2) online learning strategies; (2) teachers' experiences with implementation such as (2.1) challenges faced by teachers, (2.2) classroom management, and (2.3) pedagogical approaches; and (3) differences from previous teaching strategies such as (3.1) student engagement and interaction and (3.2) flexibility and accessibility. Based on the findings, public high schools have employed various teaching strategies, including collaborative and interactive approaches, and face-to-face instruction supplemented with video lessons. The teachers' experiences associated with these strategies were largely positive, with increased student engagement and improved academic performance reported. Additionally, the study highlights the differences between the new normal teaching strategies and previous approaches, emphasizing enhanced student socialization, active participation, and technology integration. The implications of the findings include the need for professional development programs, technology integration, supportive classroom environments, continuous assessment and feedback, equity considerations, and further research.

Keywords: *collaborative learning, interactive learning, new normal, public high schools, teaching strategies*

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic has left a major worldwide impact on educational systems, causing widespread suffering and loss of life (Schleicher, 2020). It has affected the economy and health and left a lasting impact on education. The emergence of COVID-19 led to a global public health emergency, resulting in restrictions on non-essential movements to control the spread of the virus (Chaturvedi, 2020; Saha et al., 2020). Schools were closed as a preventive measure, leading to a greater need for distance learning, including online and modular approaches. Over 1.52 billion students were unable to attend school during lockdowns and quarantines, affecting a large proportion of the global student population (UNESCO, 2020). Distance learning became a prominent feature of the new normal, posing challenges for teachers in ensuring continuous learning.

Many teachers faced difficulties in adapting to online teaching tools and methods, as well as conducting assessments and exams to maintain academic integrity and prevent cheating (Dayagbil et al., 2021). According to Kotowski et al. (2021), the increased workload associated with preparing for online classes, creating digital materials, and grading assignments resulted in burnout and stress among teachers. Additionally, Rabacal et al. (2020) found that the pandemic had negatively affected the mental health of teachers, leading to anxiety, depression, and stress.

Flexible learning has replaced traditional learning in educational systems as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, to maintain inclusive and accessible education through online, offline, or mixed teaching and learning methods, flexible learning combines digital and non-digital technologies (Santiago et al., 2021). To maintain teaching and learning continuity, higher education institutions had to adjust to flexible teaching and learning modalities, recalibrate the curriculum, equip the faculty, modernize the infrastructure, implement a strategic plan, and evaluate every part of the plan, strengthening teaching strategies to ensure the efficacy of teaching and learning processes (Dayagbil et al., 2021). Strong teacher-student interactions have long been seen as a key component of a healthy school experience (Cook et al., 2017). Moreover, Johnson and Labelle (2017) found that students prefer teachers who have an authentic, conversational style. When teachers are passionate about the material, it inspires the students to invest more time and effort in learning.

Schools gradually reopened for face-to-face classes in the Philippines as vaccination rates increased and COVID-19 cases decreased. By August 2022, schools had reopened for in-person classes, and full face-to-face instruction became mandatory in November 2022. However, these transitions between different modes of instruction pose challenges for both teachers and students in adapting to the changes. As schools reopened and transitioned back to face-to-face classes, it is important to explore the teaching strategies used during the new normal. This study provided valuable insights into the effectiveness of different instructional approaches and the challenges faced by teachers. This study explored various teaching strategies used by public high school teachers in the new normal. The findings provided insights into the effectiveness of different teaching

strategies, guiding educators in selecting and implementing pedagogical approaches that enhance student engagement and learning outcomes.

Research Questions

This study specifically aimed to explore the teaching strategies used in public high schools during the new normal. Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following:

1. What teaching strategies have been commonly used?
2. What are the teachers' experiences associated with the implementation of these teaching strategies?
3. How do these new normal strategies differ from previous strategies?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed the Transcendental Phenomenology approach developed by Husserl (1964) to effectively describe the lived experiences of teachers in the new normal. Transcendental Phenomenology is a qualitative research method aimed at uncovering the significance and meaning of lived experiences as perceived by individuals (Neubauer et al., 2019). This approach emphasizes understanding the subjective perspectives, perceptions, and interpretations of participants regarding a specific phenomenon. Furthermore, phenomenology focuses on the lived experiences themselves and how they are expressed through those experiences (Morley, 2017). This analysis provided insights into the teaching strategies and experiences of teachers, highlighting their differences from previous teaching methods.

The participants of the study were six (6) public high school teachers from Valencia National High School, Valencia City, Bukidnon, Philippines. Employing nonprobability availability sampling methods, specifically purposive and convenience sampling, the teachers were chosen as participants in the study based on their availability and willingness. The researchers only invited teachers who have been employed for at least five (5) years in the same school, from 2010 to 2024, those who were employed pre- and during the COVID-19 pandemic. This ensured the comparability of experiences and teaching strategies before and after the changes brought by the pandemic affected their teaching strategies. Informed consent forms were prepared following the ethical guidelines and were provided to all participants. These forms clearly outlined the purpose of the study, the procedures involved, and participants' rights, including their right to withdraw from the study at any time without penalty.

This study used open-ended interview questions. The data gathering process included an initial survey of public high school teachers in Valencia City, Bukidnon. This study is limited only to public high school teachers of Valencia National High School who have taught in the same school for at least five years. The researchers chose the participants based on availability and willingness to participate in the study. Once consent was secured, the researchers conducted a face-to-face interview with the public high

schoolteachers following the interview protocol. The interview was conducted at the convenience of the participants.

Instrument validation involves assessing the effectiveness and quality of research questions and interview questions to achieve efficient outcomes. Researchers must be aware of the essential approvals required before initiating a research project (Tsang et al., 2017). Three subject matter experts in the field of Education reviewed and validated the research questions and the set of interview questions used for the study using an assessment form which was divided into three key areas. The evaluators were asked to determine the validity in terms of the clarity, suitability, and understandability of the instrument in three areas namely, Introductory Key Components, Questions, and Closing Key Components, by providing their remarks and “Yes” or “No” rating on the items measured in the study.

The SME’s inter-rater reliability test shows an 89.47% agreement among them as to the validity and appropriateness of the interview questions. The result of the validation revealed the strengths and weaknesses of the interview questions as the instrument of the study. The SME's comments provided insights into what needs to be improved in the instrument of the study. Several adjustments were made to improve the instrument. The suggestions and comments from the Subject Matter Experts were used in revising the initial interview questions. A detailed research proposal outlining the study objectives, methodology, potential risks to participants, and measures for protecting their rights was prepared. This proposal was submitted to the Subject Matter Expert (SME) for review and validation.

The researcher examined the teachers’ lived experiences using the phenomenological data analysis technique. The meaning of the themes is anchored through the work of Moustakas (1994) as stated by Greening (2019) which follows the four (4) major steps of the qualitative data analysis framework that was used in the study of Clementir et al. (2022). The following four steps were used in exploring the lived experience of the teachers in the new normal and their teaching strategies:

Step 1: Significant Statements (Bracketing) - this procedure identifies pre-existing notions and viewpoints about the issue under study and keeps in reserve specific statements that give details about respondents' experiences from transcripts. These statements were selected from the transcripts and provided a better understanding of the phenomena (Moustakas, 1994).

Step 2: Meaning Units or Themes (Intuiting) - statements that were redundant and unrelated to the objective of the article had to be removed. The remaining significant statements should then be carefully evaluated by grouping them into units or themes (Moustakas, 1994). They will then be paired with related studies that share similar ideas.

Step 3: Textural and Structural Descriptions (Analyzing)- both textural and structural methods were used to describe the phenomenon. The themes were combined to describe the texture, or "what," which was then subjected to several perspectives or imaginative

adjustments to comprehend the fundamentals of the structure, or “how” (Moustakas, 1994).

Step 4: Essence of the Lived Experience (Describing)- this is the last stage of the procedure, which offers differentiations and essential explanations of the relevant experience that was recorded from the data that was extracted.

RESULTS

The data presented in this section are based on the interview conducted by the researchers on six teachers from Valencia National High School, Valencia City, Bukidnon. After every interview, the codes were fully identified by the researchers. The information was categorized and recorded. Three significant themes emerged following a phenomenological data analysis technique of the data gathered.

DISCUSSION

The following is a list of the themes and codes that came out of the interviews.

Theme 1: Commonly Used Teaching Strategies

The results highlight the use of Collaborative and Interactive Teaching Strategies in public high schools. These strategies aim to enhance collaboration and interaction not only between teachers and students but also among the students themselves. These strategies emphasize the effectiveness of collaborative and interactive approaches in promoting student engagement and learning outcomes.

Sub-theme 1.1: Collaborative and Interactive Strategies

The participants were asked what teaching strategy they used transitioning from distance learning to face-to-face instruction. A common theme that emerged was the use of

Collaborative and Interactive Teaching Strategies. Better cooperation and communication between educators and students, as well as amongst students themselves, are made possible by these strategies. These strategies were demonstrated in the statements that follow:

Teacher 1: Normally question and answer ra gyud ko sa ilaha sir. Uh, I will ask questions, dayon with their answers, gina process nako siya kay didto ko mosulod. (Normally, I implement question and answer on them, sir. I will ask them questions and then process their answers to assess what they know and what they don't know.)

Teacher 2: One strategy I use is cooperative learning.

Teacher 3: Ga apply gyud ko og kadtong peer tutorial, or like think-pair-and-share na strategy nga e explain nimo sa isa, then sila na dayon bahala mag explain sa katapad or kauban nila. (I really apply peer tutorial, or think-pair-and-share strategy in which you will explain to one student and then they will be the one to explain to their groupmates.)

Teacher 4: I have games... So that they will enjoy the new situation in the classroom.

Teacher 5: I gave lots of activities wherein they were able to actually to group - regroup – with their peers. So that the communication stage that was lost to the COVID time mura siyag (to somewhat) ma patch up ra siya.

One frequently mentioned strategy in the study is Inquiry-Based Question and Answer. This approach allows teachers to facilitate better interactions with their students by posing thought-provoking questions and encouraging active participation. Moreover, participants reported using this strategy as a means to assess students' knowledge and identify any gaps in understanding. The use of inquiry-based methods in teaching has been supported by the study of Gholam and Petro (2019), stating that Inquiry-Based Learning increases student engagement and fosters a culture of fundamental and transferable learning. A study by Akcayir and Akcayir (2018) found that inquiry-based instruction improved students' critical thinking skills and academic achievement.

Cooperative Learning is another strategy commonly employed by the participants in the study. This approach involves grouping students to foster discussions and collaborative problem-solving. This strategy allows students to engage in social interaction and learn from their peers by working in groups. Cooperative learning has a positive effect on student motivation, academic achievement, and social interactions, according to a study by Kirschner et al. (2018).

Additionally, the participants mentioned the use of Learning Through Games or gamification in learning. This strategy involves incorporating game elements in the learning process to promote student engagement and active participation. Gamification is found in education enhances students' intrinsic motivation, problem-solving skills, and overall class discussion (Sailer et al., 2017). By making learning activities fun and fulfilling, the incorporation of game components and learning activities into gamified learning may boost students' intrinsic motivation (Koivisto & Hamari, 2019).

Sub-theme 1.2: Online Learning Strategies

Another theme that emerged is the use of Online Learning Teaching Strategies. These strategies are in place to allow the teachers to adapt to unexpected class disruptions. They also practice these strategies to maximize the time and encourage students to learn in advance or to go over previous lessons that were unclear to them. These strategies were manifested in the following statements below:

Teacher 2: Video lessons no, I have prepared already the lessons on some topics... Kung moingon sila na wala sa klase karon ang mga bata, asynchronous sa ta karon provide activity. (I have prepared video lessons on some topics. If the school heads announce that there will be no classes, then we can proceed to asynchronous class.)

Teacher 3: Video lessons, so uh before nag balik ang new normal, aside from radio-based instruction, aside from modular distance learning and asynchronous online learning, naa pud mi gihimo na video lessons. (Before the transition to the new normal, aside from radio-based instruction, modular distance learning, and asynchronous online learning, we have made video lessons as a way of learning.)

Teacher 6: Using lesson videos and uh going to flip classroom, I gave them a video and after that I processed the video when they are going to have a lesson.

The results also reveal the adoption of Online Learning Teaching Strategies in public high schools. These strategies are implemented to address unexpected class disruptions and optimize learning opportunities for students. By adjusting to issues and encouraging student participation, online learning systems are demonstrated to be effective.

One prominent theme that emerged from the study is the use of Asynchronous Learning strategies in the form of pre-recorded video discussions. This approach allows teachers to adapt to class disruptions by providing students with recorded video lessons that they can access at their convenience. This strategy enables students to learn in advance, review previous lessons, or revisit unclear concepts. The use of asynchronous learning aligns with recent studies in the field of online education, it positively impacts student performance, engagement, and satisfaction (Means et al., 2019).

Furthermore, the participants emphasized the importance of online learning strategies for maximizing instructional time. These strategies enable teachers to make the most of limited synchronous class time by utilizing online resources and activities. This finding is supported by a study conducted by Barbour et al. (2019), which highlights the significant role of online learning in optimizing instructional time, especially in contexts where disruptions are frequent or unexpected.

Theme 2: Teachers' Experiences with Implementation

The results of the study provide insight into the challenges faced by educators during the transition from distance learning to face-to-face instruction in public high schools. Despite the implementation of various teaching strategies, participants encountered difficulties

related to student attitudes, learning gaps, and readiness. However, they were able to overcome these challenges by employing pedagogical approaches that enhanced the effectiveness of their teaching strategies.

Sub-theme 2.1: Challenges Faced by Teachers

The participants were asked what their experiences were with the implementation of their current teaching strategies. A common theme that emerged is that they all faced challenges in the shift to face-to-face instruction such as the student's attitude, individual differences, adjustment, isolation because of the lockdown, and the student's learning gap. These challenges were manifested in the statements below:

Teacher 1: Uh, challenges, first is the attitude of the children, the learners, they're quite different and, of course ang lesson gyud sir lisod kaayo sa ilaha pag adapt sa... sa competency. (Challenges, first is the attitude of the children, the learners, they are quite different, and of course the lesson, they are having a hard time adapting to the competency.)

Teacher 3: Sa academically, naay uban maka adjust, naay uban na dili gyud. Dayon bisag sa mga basic lang siya na concept is ga lisod sila. (Academically, some students can adjust while the others cannot. They are having difficulties even in basic concepts.)

Teacher 4: Students have difficulty shifting to the new normal because many of them were confined inside their rooms.

Teacher 5: One is the learning competencies essential for the learning of our students. A lot of students did not understand the essential topics for the next grade level.

One significant challenge mentioned by the participants was student disinterest and lack of attention during face-to-face class discussions. This finding aligns with a study conducted by Fredricks et al. (2016), which emphasizes the importance of student engagement in the learning process. Addressing disinterest and lack of attention requires teachers to employ innovative pedagogical approaches to capture students' interest and maintain their focus.

The participants also highlighted the presence of learning gaps, particularly in basic concepts, among students. This challenge is supported by studies such as the one conducted by Hattie et al. (2016), which emphasizes the significance of addressing students' prior knowledge and misconceptions to promote effective learning. Overcoming learning gaps requires teachers to identify and address students' individual needs through differentiated instruction and targeted support.

Furthermore, the participants expressed difficulties in discussing the appropriate competency level with students due to their limited understanding of previous lessons. This challenge aligns with a study conducted by Boaler et al. (2016), which emphasizes the importance of building a strong foundation of fundamental concepts for effective learning progression. Addressing this issue requires teachers to employ strategies such

as formative assessment and targeted remediation to bridge the learning gap and ensure students are adequately prepared for subsequent grade levels.

Sub-theme 2.2: Classroom Management

In addition to the other challenges faced by the participants in the shifting of classes from distance learning into face-to-face instruction, they also experienced challenges in their classroom management, which were manifested in the statements below:

Teacher 1: Gubot kaayo ang classroom, wala'y discipline ang mga bata. (The classroom is disorganized and the students have no discipline.)

Teacher 2: And with regards na dayon sa lesson, sa classroom na dayon na setting, sa topic lisod kaayo isulod sa ilaha, it's because for two years wala sila'y kaning, uh deepening of understanding sa mga competency no or sa mga topic. (With regards to the lesson, in the classroom setting, they find the topic very difficult because for two years, they do not have a deepening of understanding in the competencies or topics.)

Teacher 5: Kay ang students dili kaayo sila maminaw in terms of sa klase, kay lahi ang uh, behavior wise, lahi sila. (The students do not usually listen in the class, because behavior wise, they are quite different.)

Despite the teaching strategies being implemented, the participants encountered a challenge in their classroom management. Participants said that their classroom is messy because the students have no discipline, they do not listen in class, and they have different behaviors, making it difficult to handle them and implement their teaching strategies.

Exclusionary discipline results in lost classroom instruction time, which has a detrimental impact on students nationwide, participants believed positive reinforcement, academic support, behavior support, relationships, planning, and teaching expectations and consequences were the most effective classroom management strategies (Maness, 2021). Since the beginning of education, teachers have had to figure out how to control their classes and deal with unruly pupils (Gahungu, 2018).

Participants highlighted the significant learning gap experienced by students due to nearly two years of disrupted classes during the pandemic, which has led to a decline in student performance. Research indicates that effective classroom management is linked to improved academic outcomes (Gage et al., 2017; George et al., 2017; State et al., 2019). Such management practices optimize the use of various strategies, including interactive classroom structures, teaching and reinforcing expectations, and maintaining active student engagement in lessons and activities (Grasley-Boy et al., 2019).

Sub-theme 2.3: Pedagogical Approaches

Concerning the challenges faced by the participants in the shifting of class from distance learning to face-to-face instruction, they were able to come up with different pedagogical

approaches that made their teaching strategies more effective. These challenges were manifested in the statements below:

Teacher 1: We have drills... ma train ang mga bata... until now gasige pa japon mi og drills sir kay affected gihapon ang mga bata sa adtong mga lessons na ilang na behind. At least man lang na ma train ba, ma practice ilang brain to work on it. (We have drills to train the students. We have drills until now because the students were affected for those lessons that they are behind. At least, they can be trained, to practice their brain to work on it.)

Teacher 2: Nag evolve siya, nadungagan among skills sa technology... so pag abot sa, pag balik sa face-to-face, mas equipped mi, mas daghan mig strategies nga amoang mahatag sa mga bata. (It evolved, we have acquired and learned new skills in technology. That is why when we shift back to face-to-face, we are equipped and we have various strategies we can apply to the students.)

Teacher 3: So, students ang mag explain sa front, sila ang mag explain kung gi unsa. If ever man gyud kung walay students na maka answer, that's the time nga ayha pa dayon ko mo in para ma explain sa ilaha. (The students will explain in front, they will explain how they did it. If ever there are no students who cannot answer, that will be the cue when I will be the one explaining to them.)

Teacher 4: One realization on that transition is that learning doesn't only take place inside the classroom, it also takes place whenever you can guide the students to learn a specific lesson.

Teacher 5: Sometimes we have to undergo one-on-one tutoring to students for those who don't really have the knowledge. Kadtong sa mga studyante na galisod jud (for those students who are really having a hard time).

Teacher 6: The problem there is the readiness of the students, so I give them drills related to basic concepts and sometimes tutor them when needed.

Despite these challenges, participants successfully enhanced their teaching effectiveness through diverse pedagogical approaches. One participant who employed Inquiry-Based Learning described assessing students' understanding through trial and error, enabling them to actively engage in the learning process. This method aligns with findings from Kuhn et al. (2017), which emphasize the advantages of inquiry-based instruction in fostering critical thinking and problem-solving skills.

Participants practicing Cooperative Learning addressed performance issues by incorporating drills and guided activities related to the topics. This approach aligns with a study conducted by Slavin (2015), which emphasizes the positive impact of cooperative learning on student achievement and motivation. Moreover, participants using video lessons mentioned the evolution of teaching strategies and the ability to adapt to unexpected class disruptions. This adaptability aligns with a study conducted by Hew and Chung (2016), which highlights the flexibility and accessibility of online resources in supporting student learning in diverse contexts. According to Monroe et al., (2010) as stated by Maness (2021), it has been identified that classroom management is one of the most influential factors in determining success for first-year teachers and as the most influential factor in students' academic success.

Theme 3: Differences from Previous Teaching Strategies

The results highlight the positive impact of the current teaching environment on student engagement, socialization, and academic performance. Teachers have been able to build rapport with their students, leading to improved student reactions and appreciation for face-to-face classes.

Sub-theme 3.1: Student Engagement and Interaction

The participants were asked how their current teaching strategies differed from the strategies they used before returning to face-to-face classes. During the distance learning, they had little to no interaction with their students since their strategy only involved distributing modules and checking students' answers. With the current teaching environment, the teachers are now able to build rapport with their students. These challenges were manifested in the statements below:

Teacher 1: Kadtong transition sa pandemic time sir, okay kaayo ang mga teacher, since dili man maka afford ang mga bata to provide internet and ana, okay kaayo akong work – relax – kay I'll only check the work of the children, the learners. (In the transition to the pandemic time sir, the teachers are very good. Since the children cannot provide internet and the likes, my work is comfortable and relaxing, because I'll only check the work of the children, the learners.)

Teacher 2: Sa mga students, positive sad sir... mas na appreciate jud sa mga bata ang face-to-face. (For the students, it was positive sir, they really appreciate face-to-face classes.)

Teacher 3: Learners uh learners were able to manage, uh unsa ni, kanang, learning together as a group. (Learners were able to manage learning together as a group.)

Teacher 4: Sa karon ang mga bata nahinay hinay nag ka socialize. (For now, the children slowly adapting and socializing.)

Teacher 5: Karon ma master na gyud nila ang integers, in which mao gyud siya ang pinaka basic sa math. (Now, the students have already mastered integers which is the very basic topic in math.)

Teacher 6: Some directly embrace it... Some, their grades somehow increase.

Participants who employed collaborative and interactive teaching strategies reported heightened student engagement and peer interaction. This aligns with research by Johnson et al. (2018), which highlights the advantages of collaborative learning in fostering active participation, socialization, and higher-order thinking skills. The improved socialization and active involvement of students in class discussions during face-to-face instruction further reinforce the idea that interactive strategies enhance both student experiences and academic performance.

Moreover, participants observed an improvement in students' academic performance since returning to face-to-face classes and implementing drills and guided activities. This finding aligns with a study conducted by Hattie (2017), which highlights the positive impact

of classroom-based activities and formative assessments on student learning and achievement. The use of guided activities and targeted drills enables teachers to provide immediate feedback and support, fostering student progress and academic growth.

Sub-theme 3.2: Flexibility and Accessibility

A common theme that emerged among participants that use online learning strategies such as asynchronous learning in the form of video lessons, is better flexibility and accessibility in their discussions.

Teacher 2: Makahimo na dayon ko og kanang powerpoint na maka, or unsa ba kaha na presentation na pwede ra nako ma send via messenger ba kaha, via gmail, or kung dako dako didto gyud sa google drive no, sa mga bata. (I can now make PowerPoint presentations in which I could send it via messenger, Gmail, or upload it in the google drive for easy access of the students.)

Teacher 3: Labi na kung, say for example, wala mi klase kay naa mi activities na apilan, magamit gyud namo siya. (Most especially, for example, if we do not have a class because we have something to attend, we can easily use those materials.)

Teacher 6: You can really somehow have the continuous learning of the learners even though there are conditions that somehow will not permit the face-to-face learning.

Participants utilizing online learning strategies, such as asynchronous learning through video lessons, highlighted the benefits of flexibility and accessibility in their teaching discussions. The ability to adapt quickly to class disruptions and ensure continuous learning aligns with a study conducted by Hew and Cheung (2016), which emphasizes the advantages of online learning in providing flexible learning opportunities and overcoming barriers to face-to-face instruction. The use of video lessons as supplemental discussions further enhances accessibility for students, enabling them to revisit and review content outside of the classroom.

Conclusions

This study examined the teaching strategies employed by public high schools in the new normal, focusing on teachers' experiences with their implementation. The findings revealed that a variety of strategies were commonly utilized, including collaborative and interactive approaches, as well as supplemental video lessons. These results underscore the diverse methods teachers are using to facilitate student learning in the current educational landscape.

Teachers' experiences with implementing these strategies were largely positive. Participants reported successfully building rapport with their students, which led to increased engagement and improved academic performance. The collaborative and interactive strategies were particularly effective in promoting student interaction and participation, thereby enhancing the overall learning experience. Moreover, the

integration of online learning methods, such as asynchronous video lessons, offered flexibility and accessibility for both teachers and students.

The study also highlighted the distinctions between the new normal teaching strategies and previous approaches. During the distance learning phase, teachers faced limited interaction with students and mainly relied on distributing and checking modules. In contrast, the shift to face-to-face instruction enabled teachers to conduct in-person classes, which fostered greater student socialization and active participation in discussions. Current strategies also emphasize the use of drills and guided activities, contributing to improved academic performance among students.

Recommendations

Based study's findings, the following recommendations are proposed for educators, policymakers, and educational institutions.

Invest in comprehensive professional development programs that equip teachers with the necessary skills and competencies and encourage the integration of technology into teaching practices to enhance flexibility and accessibility, thereby improving technological skills, fostering innovative approaches to online learning, and effectively implementing collaborative and interactive teaching strategies.

Encourage teachers to create opportunities for collaborative learning, peer interaction, and meaningful class discussions. Implement formative assessment strategies that allow for continuous monitoring of student progress and provide timely feedback. Encourage teachers to use guided activities, drills, and other targeted assessments to gauge student understanding and provide individualized support where needed.

Encourage further research to explore the long-term effects of teaching strategies, conduct comparative analyses of different instructional approaches, and investigate the impact of technology integration on student outcomes.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

A comprehensive research proposal was developed that outlined the study's objectives, methodology, potential risks to participants, and measures to protect their rights. This proposal was submitted to the Subject Matter Expert (SME) for review and validation. Informed consent forms were created in accordance with ethical guidelines and distributed to all participants. These forms clearly explained the study's purpose, the procedures involved, and participants' rights, including their right to withdraw from the study at any time without penalty.

To ensure the confidentiality of participants' information, several steps were taken. The data collected during the study were anonymized and securely stored to prevent unauthorized access. Only members of the research team had access to the data, and any identifying information was removed prior to analysis. Measures were also implemented to minimize potential harm or discomfort to participants, including

conducting the study in a manner that respects their dignity, privacy, and autonomy. Support resources were provided for participants who might experience adverse effects due to their involvement in the study. The research was conducted in line with ethical guidelines and principles, emphasizing honesty, integrity, and respect for the participants' rights and welfare.

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REFERENCES

- Akcayir, M., & Akcayir, G. (2018). The flipped classroom: A review of its advantages and challenges. *Computers & Education*, 126, 334-345.
- Barbour, M. K., Brown, R., & Waters, L. H. (2019). A snapshot of K-12 online and blended learning in Michigan: Past, present, and future. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, 51(4), 380-397.
- Boaler, J., Chen, L., Williams, C., & Cordero, M. (2016). Seeing as understanding: The importance of visual mathematics for our brain and learning. *Journal of Applied & Computational Mathematics*, 5(6), 313-322.
- Chaturvedi, K., Vishwakarma, D., Singh, N. (2020, December 5). COVID-19 and its impact on education, social life and mental health of students: A survey. *Child Youth Serv Rev*. 2021 Feb; 121: 105866.
- Clementir, M., Cotamora, M. J. A., Pineda, G. C., Tan, D. (2022). A Phenomenological Study on Parental Involvement in the Completion of Students' Learning Task in Science under Modular Distance Learning. *IJASR 2022. VOLUME 5 ISSUE 6 NOVEMBER - DECEMBER*. ISSN: 2581-7876.
- Cook, C., Coco, S., Zhang, Y., Fiat, A., Duong, M., Renshaw, T., Long, A., & Frank, S. (2017). Cultivating Positive Teacher–Student Relationships: Preliminary Evaluation of the Establish–Maintain–Restore (EMR) Method. *School Psychology Review*. Volume 47, Issue 3.
- Dayagbil FT, Palompon DR, Garcia LL & Olvido MMJ. (2021, July 23). Teaching and Learning Continuity Amid and Beyond the Pandemic. *Front. Educ*. 6:678692.
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (1985). *Intrinsic motivation and self-determination in human behavior*. New York, NY: Springer.
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2008). Self-determination theory: A macrotheory of human motivation, development, and health. *Canadian Psychology/Psychologie canadienne*, 49(3), 182-185.
- Farsawang, P., & Songkram, N. (2023). Fostering technology integration and adaptability in higher education: Insights from the COVID-19 pandemic. *Contemporary Educational Technology*. <https://doi.org/10.30935/cedtech/13513>.
- Fredricks, J. A., Blumenfeld, P. C., & Paris, A. H. (2016). School engagement: Potential of the concept, state of the evidence. *Review of Educational Research*, 86(3), 721-746.

- Gage, N. A., Adamson, R., MacSuga-Gage, A. S., & Lewis, T. J. (2017). The relation between the academic achievement of students with emotional and behavioral disorders and teacher characteristics. *Behavioral Disorders*, 43(1), 213–222.
- Gahungu, A. (2018). Indiscipline and safety in public schools: Teachers and principals at odds. *International Journal of Research in Education and Science*, 4(2), 375–390.
- George, I. N., Sakirudeen, A. O., & Sunday, A. H. (2017). Effective classroom management and students' academic performance in secondary schools in Uyo local government area of Akwa Ibom State. *Research in Pedagogy*, 7(1), 43–56.
- Gholam, A. (2019). Inquiry-Based Learning: Student Teachers' Challenges and Perceptions. *Journal of Inquiry & Action in Education*, 10(2).
- Grasley-Boy, N., Gage, N. A., & MacSuga-Gage, A. S. (2019). Multitiered support for classroom management professional development. *Beyond Behavior*, 28(1), 5–12.
- Hattie, J. (2017). The power of feedback. *Review of Educational Research*, 77(1), 81-112.
- Hattie, J., Fisher, D., & Frey, N. (2016). *Visible learning for mathematics, grades K-12: What works best to optimize student learning*. Corwin Press.
- Hew, K. F., & Cheung, W. S. (2016). Students' and instructors' use of massive open online courses (MOOCs): Motivations and challenges. *Educational Research Review*, 18, 105-129.
- Husserl, E. (1964). The train of thoughts in lectures. In C. Polifroni & M. Welch (Eds.), *Perspectives on philosophy of science in nursing* (pp. 247-262). Philadelphia, PA: Lippincott
- Johnson, D. W., Johnson, R. T., & Roseth, C. J. (2018). Cooperative learning in 21st century. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 69, 275-301.
- Johnson, Z. & Labelle, S. (2017). An examination of teacher authenticity in the college classroom. *Communication Education*. Volume 66, Issue 4.
- Kirschner, P. A., Sweller, J., & Clark, R. E. (2018). *Educational psychology: Teaching for effective learning*. Springer.
- Koivisto, J., & Hamari, J. (2019). The rise of motivational information systems: A review of gamification research. *International Journal of Information Management*, 45, 191–210. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2018.10.013>
- Kotowski, S., Davis, K., & Barratt, C. (2021). Teachers feeling the burden of COVID-19: Impact on well-being, stress, and burnout. *Work*, vol. 71, no. 2, pp. 407-415, 2022.
- Kuhn, D., Van Zee, E., & Fasulo, A. (2017). Developing norms of argumentation: Metacognitive, epistemological, and social dimensions of developing argumentative competence. *Cognition and Instruction*, 35(2), 97-124.
- Maness, J. A. (2021). "Effective classroom management strategies, professional development needs, and policy recommendations for reducing discipline infractions". *Theses and Dissertations*. 5122.
- Means, B., Bakia, M., & Murphy, R. (2019). *Teaching online in K–12: Models, methods, and best practices for teachers and administrators*. Routledge.
- Monroe, A. E., Blackwell, S. E., & Pepper, S. K. (2010). Strengthening professional development partnerships while bridging classroom management instruction and practice. *Professional Educator*, 34(2), 18–26.
- Morley, J., Giorgi, A., & Giorgi, B. (2017). The Descriptive Phenomenological Psychological Method. <https://dx.doi.org/10.4135/9781526405555.n11>
- Moustakas, C. E. (1994). *Phenomenological research methods*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications
- Neubauer, B. E., Witkop, C. T., & Varpio, L. (2019). How phenomenology can help us learn from the experiences of others. *Perspectives on Medical Education*, 8(2), 90–97.
- Rabacal, J., Oducado, R. & Tamdang, K. (2020). COVID-19 Impact on the Quality of Life of Teachers: A Cross-sectional Study. *Research Note*, Vol. 8, Issue 4, 2020.

- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2000). Self-determination theory and the facilitation of intrinsic motivation, social development, and well-being. *American Psychologist*, 55(1), 68-78.
- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2017). *Self-determination theory: Basic psychological needs in motivation, development, and wellness*. Guilford Publications.
- Saha J., Barman B., & Chouhan P. (2020, September). Lockdown for COVID-19 and its Impact on Community Mobility in India: An Analysis of the COVID-19 Community Mobility Reports, 2020. *Children and Youth Services Review*. 2020;116.
- Sailer, M., Hense, J. U., Mayr, S. K., & Mandl, H. (2017). How gamification motivates: An experimental study of the effects of specific game design elements on psychological need satisfaction. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 69, 371-380.
- Santiago Jr., C. S., Ulanday, M. L. P., Centeno, Z. J. R., Bayla, M. C. D., & Callanta, J. S. (2021). Flexible learning adaptabilities in the new normal: E-learning resources, digital meeting platforms, online learning systems and learning engagement. *Asian Journal of Distance Education*, 16(2), 38-56.
- Schleicher, A. (2020). *The Impact of Covid-19 on Education: Insights from Education at a Glance 2020*.
- Slavin, R. E. (2015). Cooperative learning in elementary schools. *Education 3-13*, 43(1), 5-14.
- State, T. M., Simonsen, B., Hirn, R. G., & Wills, H. (2019). Bridging the research-to-practice gap through effective professional development for teachers working with students with emotional and behavioral disorders. *Behavioral Disorders*, 44(2), 107–116.
- Tsang, S., Royse, C. F., & Terkawi, A. S. (2017). Guidelines for developing, translating, and validating a questionnaire in perioperative and pain medicine. *Saudi journal of anaesthesia*, 11(Suppl 1), S80–S89. https://doi.org/10.4103/sja.SJA_203_17
- UNESCO Learning Portal (2020). Brief 3: Learning and Teaching Materials Paris.